

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MOODS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.

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Abstract. *The following article argue that the ways and problems of expressing mood categories in world linguistics analyzing them between English and Uzbek languages. Especially, the article identifies different approaches to the semantic classification of sentences of the moods in both languages.*

Key words: *Indicative mood, imperative mood, subjunctive mood, imperative-subjunctive mood, conditional mood, mood categories declarative sentence, interrogative sentence.*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ НАСТРОЕНИЙ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И
УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ.

Аннотация. *В следующей статье рассматриваются пути и проблемы выражения категорий настроения в мировой лингвистике, анализируя их между английским и узбекским языками. В частности, в статье выявляются разные подходы к семантической классификации предложений по наклонениям в обоих языках.*

Ключевые слова: *Изъявительное наклонение, повелительное наклонение, сослагательное наклонение, повелительно-сослагательное наклонение, условное наклонение, категории наклонения, повествовательное предложение, вопросительное предложение.*

Verb moods are always of looking at verbs and classifying them which show the attitude of the speaker. Verb moods are classifications that indicate the attitude of the speaker. Each language may have its own moods. Yet their types or numbers can be different or similar. According to English grammar, mood is a form of the verb that shows the relationship of action to reality. This attitude is established by the speaker. He can use the form of a verb to represent an action as real, problematic, unreal, or as a request or order. In English, as in Uzbek, there are three moods.

According to Uzbek grammar, the grammatical forms that express the relation of action to reality are called moods. Mood categories are inextricably linked with verb tenses, person-number categories. The mood means the execution of an action is connected with a real being and,

therefore, it expresses the meanings of indicative, imperative, subjunctive, and conditional. In Uzbek grammar imperative and subjunctive belongs to the same one type. Accordingly, the moods have three types: 1. Indicative; 2. Imperative and subjunctive; 3. Conditional.

1. Indicative mood of English language : The indicative mood presents an action as a real fact that happened in the past, is happening now or will happen in future. That's why it is called a real mood or a fact mood. The indicative mood is rich in forms reflecting all grammatical categories of finite verbs (the categories of person and number, tense, aspect and voice). [2;55]

E.g.: *Hurry listened anxiously, but there was no sound from the Dursleys' bedroom* [4;25]

1. Indicative mood of Uzbek language: A verb form expressing a message, a sign about the execution or non-execution of an action or situation. Indicates whether the action should be executed. This mood is formed by adding tense and person-number suffixes to the base of the verb. [3.368]

For instance: *O'zbek oyim uncha-muncha to'yu azalarga "kavshim ko'chada qolg'an emas" deb bormas edi.* [1;72]

2. Imperative mood of English language: The imperative mood actually does not give any information as to the reality of an action described by the verb. That's why some linguists do not consider the imperative form to be a mood form, though it is traditionally included in the mood system on the ground that it represents a hypothetical action. An imperative typically urges the addressee to do or not to do something. It is used to give orders or requests, and expects some action from the address. Given this limited function, most imperative clauses are characterized by the lack of a subject in the surface structure (which usually implies the addressee, i.e. the second person), by the use of the infinitive of the verb and the absence of modals as well as tense and aspect markers: [2.55]

E.g.: *"Don't worry", said Fred, and "stand back"* [4;25].

2. Imperative mood of Uzbek language: A form of a verb expressing the meaning of a command, wish, request, advice to perform or not perform an action. Imperative forms are formed by adding the following suffixes to verb bases: (a)y, -(a)yin, -gin, -(i)ng, -sin, -(a)ylik, -(i)ngs. [3.387]

E.g.: - *Bor-bor, avliya, bitta bachcha bo'lsangiz idishi bilan sizniki.* [1;86]

3. Subjunctive mood of English language: The form of present subjunctive coincides with the infinitive of the verb. Accordingly, the subjunctive form *be* is distinct from the indicative forms *am*, *is*, and *are* (e.g. *Be it as you wish.*). For other verbs, present subjunctive is distinctive only in the 3rd person singular as it does not take the inflection *-s*. Present subjunctive is used in certain set expressions: *God bless you. Long live the King. God save the Queen*, and so on. Negation of the present subjunctive does not require an operator (i.e. the auxiliary *do*). For instance: *I insist*

that the Council not reconsider its decision. The past subjunctive is identical in form with the simple past of the verb. The exception is the verb be which occurs in the past subjunctive as were with all the persons both in singular and plural. Because of this, the past subjunctive is sometimes referred to as were -subjunctive. The past subjunctive is hypothetical in meaning. It is used mostly in conditional clauses and in subordinate clauses after wish and suppose : [2.56]

“If the Dursleys wake up, I’m dead,” said Harry as he tied the rope tightly around a bar and Fred revved up the car.[4.25]

3.Subjunctive mood of Uzbek language: The mood is made using the verb and the suffix -sa, which expresses the condition for the performance or non-performance of another action and situation,as well as the desire.It also means future tense.[3.389]

E.g: *-San uylansang biz ranjirmidik?- dedi kulib hoji.[4;72]*

In summary: The comparative study of moods in the English and Uzbek languages reveals that mood categories including indicative, imperative, subjunctive, and conditional are similar in both languages. However, due to each language's distinct grammatical structures and linguistic characteristics, there might be variations in how these moods are formed and used.

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